

$F(s)$ Is Not a Function But a Constant

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this short paper is to show that $F(s)$ is not a function but a constant. Some widely-known $F(s)$'s are the Riemann zeta "function", Gamma "function", Laplace transform, and Fourier transform.

I took a quick look at the definition of a Mathematical function and confirmed to my satisfaction that it is indeed *not* a function but a *constant*.

What is a Function?

The *Encyclopedia Britannica* [1] defined the function as "... an expression, rule, or law that defines a relationship between one variable (the independent variable) and another variable (the dependent variable)".

In other words, *without an independent variable*, there is *no* function. The function f is usually denoted by $f(x)$ for real x , and $f(z)$ for complex z .

Some examples of real functions:

$$f(x) = e^{-ax}, x^2, \sin(\pi x), \ln(x), \frac{1}{x}, \text{ and } \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi x)}.$$

Some examples of complex functions:

$$f(z) = e^{-az}, z^2, \sin(\pi z), \ln(z), \frac{1}{z}, \text{ and } \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi z)}.$$

Since without an independent variable, there is no function, and if a is constant, then

$$e^{-a}, a^2, \sin(\pi a), \ln(a), \frac{1}{a}, \text{ and } \frac{\pi}{\sin(\pi a)}$$

are *constants* and *not* functions. Therefore, the functional notation $f(a)$ is *not* valid if a is constant, because $f(a)$ is *not* a function.

The Constant Parameter

A constant parameter s is always *single-valued* in $f(z)$. It belongs to a *singleton* set S , which is a set with one element, that is

$$S = \{s\}.$$

If s is a complex *variable*, then it can take on all of its valid values in $f(z)$. On the other hand, if it is constant, then it can take only *one* of those values. So, if A is the set of all valid values of s (if it is a variable) in $f(z)$, then if it is constant,

$$S = \{s \in A : s = s\}.$$

For example, $A = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$:

If $s = 3$, then $s \neq 1, 2, 4, 5$; if $s = 2$, then $s \neq 1, 3, 4, 5$; and, so on.

The Integral of a Function

Consider the exponential function

$$f(x) = e^{-ax}, \quad x \geq 0,$$

its integral from 0 to x

$$F(x) = \int_0^x e^{-at} dt = \frac{1}{a}(1 - e^{-ax})$$

is still a function. $F(x)$ is the area under the curve of $f(x)$ to the left of x . If we let x approach ∞ , the value of a must be greater zero, so that

$$F(\infty) = \frac{1}{a} = \text{constant} \quad a > 0, \quad a = a.$$

Thus, in obtaining the integral of $f(x)$ for all its possible values and with an appropriate value of a , the independent variable *disappears*, leaving us only with a constant (the total area under its curve).

The conditional statement $a > 0$ does not mean that a can take values on a continuous scale (because that would make it a variable and not a constant), but rather that its value is such that $F(\infty)$ converges.

And since a is single-valued, $F(\infty)$ is also single-valued or constant, that is

$$F(\infty) = \begin{cases} \frac{1}{a} & a = a \\ 0 & \text{not } a \end{cases} \quad a > 0.$$

The trouble is that $F(\infty)$ is usually written as $F(s)$, which gives the false idea that it is a function. So instead of $F(s)$, we should use $F\{s\}$

$$F\{s\} = \begin{cases} F(\infty) & s = s \\ 0 & \text{not } s \end{cases}$$

And so, the following are constants:

The Riemman zeta constant $\zeta\{s\} = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{n^s} \quad \Re(s) > 1, s = s;$

The Gamma constant

$$\Gamma\{s\} = \int_0^{\infty} x^{s-1} e^{-x} dx = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{n^s n!}{s(s+1)(s+2)\dots(s+n)} \quad \Re(s) > 0, s = s;$$

The Reflection Formula $\Gamma\{s\}\Gamma\{1-s\} = \frac{\pi}{\sin\{\pi s\}} \quad 0 < \Re(s) < 1, s = s;$

The Laplace transform $F\{s\} = \mathcal{L}\{f(x)\} = \int_0^{\infty} f(x) e^{-sx} dx \quad \Re(s) > 0, s = s; \text{ and}$

The Fourier transform $F\{\nu\} = \mathcal{F}\{f(x)\} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} f(t) e^{-2\pi i \nu x} dx \quad \nu \text{ is constant } \nu = \nu.$

Furthermore, because s is constant, Δs and ΔF are both zero. So that

$$\frac{\Delta F}{\Delta s} = \frac{0}{0} = \text{indeterminate}, \quad \text{and} \quad \int_s^s F\{s\} ds = 0.$$

Since both $\frac{\Delta F}{\Delta s}$ and $\frac{dF}{ds}$ do not exist, which proves once again that $F\{s\}$ is not a function.

CONCLUSION

Therefore, because s is constant and not an independent variable, $F(s)$ is not a function but a constant. And since the functional notation $F(s)$ is invalid, I denote it as $F\{s\}$.

REFERENCE

Britannica, The Editors of Encyclopaedia. "**function**". Encyclopedia Britannica, 1 Dec. 2022, <https://www.britannica.com/science/function-mathematics>. Accessed 29 April 2023.